

Benefits, limitations and expectation to animal based farm information management systems

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Abstract

The global demands of society to increase the amount of animal based food, to reduce the environmental impact and to improve animal welfare are developing parallel. In the digitalized world, livestock farming obtains new opportunities to become more efficient, transparent and animal friendly. Information and communication technologies (ICT) dominate innovation in many sectors, including food and agriculture. Farm management needs information and knowledge at different levels, from herd to individuals, to body organs or metabolism. Animals are the starting point and the aim of livestock management at these different levels. With examples from welfare management, emission control and milking technologies options will be shown how to improve the farm management in knowledge based circular bioeconomy.

Background

In the digitalized world, livestock farming obtains new opportunities to become more efficient, transparent and animal friendly. The global demands of society to increase the amount of animal based food, to reduce the environmental impact and to improve animal welfare are developing parallel. It is known that these different expectations cannot be fulfilled without conflicts. The information technology may help to improve this situation. Detailed information about “livestock’s life” and a better understanding of the highly complex systems of livestock farming and their large number of dependencies and cross reactions can help to meet the different aims in the society.

ATB livestock research group works since a long time with the conviction that improved livestock farming systems can only be developed on base of improved understanding of the life of animals and their interactions with the environment. Farm management and the development of new equipment and sensors have to follow this basic conviction.

Cattle production is of high importance in many countries of the world. Humans made cattle to the most successful animal species in the world. Economic impacts as well as the environmental impacts are reasons why our group mainly works in the field of cattle production, especially dairy production.

Farm management and ICT

Farm management as carried out by farmers has been defined as 'the process by which resources and situations are manipulated by the farm manager in trying, with less than full information, to achieve his [or her] goals' (FAO, 2017) and operates in four modes: *routine operational and control* activities, *descriptive* activities, *diagnostic* activities, *prescriptive* activities. Thus, a farm manager integrates information from the biological, physical, and social sciences in the decision process (Britannica, 2017).

Information and communication technologies (ICT) dominate innovation in many sectors, including food and agriculture. It could revolutionise the sector in the same way as tractors and chemicals did in the 1950s. Programming of research and innovation in the field of ICT in agriculture is a challenging task, as ICT is an enabling technology. It will change the way farms are operated and managed and it will change the farm structure as well as the food chain in unexplored ways – just as in the 1950s, the changes in the next three decades could not be foreseen. (EU SCAR, 2016).

In the future, farmers will have to manage information effectively to improve economic viability and to reduce environmental impact. All three levels, in which agricultural activities need to be harmonized with economic and environmental constraints, require integrated ICT adoption:

- (i) improvement of farm efficiency;
- (ii) integration of public goods provided by farming into management strategies;
- (iii) relating to the environmental and cultural diversity of Europe's agriculture by addressing the region-farm interaction (ICT-AGRI, 2017).

In the European Strategic Research Agenda ICT-AGRI (Didelot et al., 2012) the Farm Management and Information System (FMIS) is described as the backbone system for all other ICT and robotic solution domains. FMIS provides a common user interface across solution domains and a repository for farm information. It includes tools for communication and information exchange, and acts as a decision support system (DSS). Time-consuming and error-prone manual data collection may be replaced by automated information collection and storage. The FMIS of tomorrow will be a modular system.

FMIS and livestock management

Scientific papers about FMIS focus mainly on arable farming and crop production (Sørensen et al., 2010 and Fountas et al., 2015).

On the one side, FMIS in the livestock sector has to integrate different parts of a farm as well as different levels within the production process. On the other side, it should handle all exchanges of information within a circular bioeconomy and with the consumers (Figure 1). An example is the expected information exchange about results of "omics"-analyses and their use for management decisions (ATF, 2016).

Figure 1. Farm management and information system (FMIS) as a tool to connect information driven processes in a livestock farm and with those in the society

Farm management needs information and knowledge at different levels, from herd to individuals, to body organs or metabolism. In our institute the research is focussed on three topics:

“Welfare management”, “emission control” and “milking technique”.

We see them as tools for future FMIS in livestock farming.

Welfare management

At our research farm we collect continuously or periodically a lot of data from cows, such as breathing, rumination, activity and localisation, heart rate variability, rumen pH, body temperature, milk quantity and quality and milking behaviour, or feed intake. Additionally there are information about the climate conditions inside and outside the barn available. Relations between climate conditions and behaviour are of interest, especially in hot situations. In a first step, the strong correlation between the respiration rate of high yielding dairy cows and the temperature-humidity-index (THI) was identified (Figure 2). Now, the analyses are more detailed to identify individuality of the reactions and the reasons behind the different behaviour.

Figure 2. Respiration rate of high yielding dairy cows and THI in a dairy barn in Northeast Germany

Emission control

Odour, ammonia and greenhouse gases are relevant for the neighbourhood, ecosystems and the atmosphere. That is why mitigating strategies are necessary. In an open and naturally ventilated barn there are not so many options to control emissions. ATB uses modern research facilities for three pillars (field measurement, physical modelling in a wind tunnel and numerical modelling) and combines the methods for validation and further development. A first result is the control of air stream through the barn by the help of curtains (Figure 3).

Curtain: bottom closed

Curtain: top and bottom closed

Figure 3. Influence of curtain positions to the airflow through a dairy barn (Results of numerical modelling at ATB)

Another project to control emissions deals with methane and feeding strategy. This study aims to evaluate the GHG emissions in dairy farms, through the analysis of the effect of different diets on the emissions from dairy cows at laboratory scale and the use of a model to estimate the GHG emissions at real farm conditions (Menardo et al, 2017). The individual reactions to the different diets are very interesting. May be there is a change to develop individualised low emission feeding strategies with the help of information technology.

Milking technique

Being precise and udder friendly with milking needs quarter specific technology. It is well known that the four quarters of an udder are independent, have different productivity and different milking behaviour. Since long time, breeders of dairy cattle focused on this topic. We analysed the milking process over one year in a farm with nine voluntary milking systems (VMS) from DeLaval to see the recent situation in a German Holstein herd. The results in detail: rear quarters have 1 kg more milk per milking than front quarters; left and right quarters do not significantly differ in milk production; there were no significant differences in milk flow between the quarters. In consequence, the milking time of the rear quarters is 1 min longer than this of the front quarters. This difference was significant as well (Heinicke et al., 2015). These results underline the motivation for further research in quarter specific milking technique. Steps are the reduction of vacuum with decreasing milk flow (Ströbel et al., 2013) and the division of the teat cup functions (adhesion and milking) with a new construction of the teat cup (Ströbel et al., 2016).

Conclusion

The fast development in ICT influences livestock farming in different ways. Farm management systems have to fulfil a lot of different expectations. With further automation in the livestock sector the importance of decision support systems an artificial intelligence increases. Most of the information, which are necessary to manage farm animals, are not directly measurable. Thus, different sensors have to collect data to get information, for example about the health status of an animal. It seems to be helpful to follow a hierarchic architecture for FMIS in livestock farming. So processes to handle a robot should be firstly oriented to this aim, but some relevant information can go up to next level. At this level the communication between different robots may be located. Further levels should be the complete farm and the interactions between the partners in the value chain.

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